

A STUDY ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper, based on the theory of fracture, propose the hypothesis of three stages of fracture procedure by examining the behaviors of practical fracture of carbon fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites, and mainly discuss the stable crack propagation energy (SCPE). Through three-point bending and chevron notch specimens test, the method of calculating SCPE is given out, and the SCPE can be expected as the parameter of fracture toughness of this composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fibers reinforced ceramic matrix composites, compared with monolithic ceramics, have much greater works of fracture, up to several tens KJm^{-2} , comparable with polymer matrix composites. Linear elastic fracture mechanics is not applicable to these materials and therefore numbers quoted as critical or candidate stress intensity factors are of little value. However the high damage tolerance which these values of work of fracture imply is of value for applications where the components are at risk of damage in service, while under stress.^{1,2} In this context how to investigate these materials using new parameter has now become an interesting topic.

2. THREE STAGES OF CRACK PROPAGATION

The new parameter for material toughness shall be satisfied:

1. the matrix crack growth in steady-state, and
2. kept the interface shear stress in proper value, that make the composites having the high work of fracture.

Referring to the crack growth in the metal, the hypothesis is used that the process of crack propagation in composites can be divided into three stages. First, it is

Fig.1 three stages of fracture procedure

the stable propagation (Fig.1.1). The microcrack in the tip of notch grows into the macrocrack and propagates stably. In this stage, matrix and fibers bear together the

applied load and the stress concentration of notch, the interface of fiber and matrix is not apart from each other, because there is little crack opening displacement. The second stage is the sub-stable propagation stage (Fig.1.2). As the applied load increases the crack opening displacement becomes greater, although some fibers are pulled out, they are still intact. These fibers like bridge in the crack surface have a closure effect. With the load increasing, the fibers are gradually pulled out and failure occurs as the crack grows. Finally, it is the unstable propagation stage (Fig.1.3). At this time, the applied load is greater than the strength limit of composites, fibers are broken, crack propagates rapidly, and the specimen fails. At the three stage, the greater the bond between fiber and matrix is, the longer the first stage becomes. It depends upon the strength of fiber and matrix, the interfacial bond, and the residual stress of composites. In the second stage the crack grows with the intact fibers pulled out and broken. For matrix, the drive force in the tip of crack is greater than its resistance to crack, but the propagation is restrained by the closure effect of fibers. This stage is determined by the strength of fiber and the interfacial bond. In essential, the stage of fiber pull-out is a stage of the interfacial damage accumulation. At the final stage, fibers are broken, crack unstably propagates. So the stable crack propagation energy (SCPE) in the first stage can be taken as parameter prescribing the fracture toughness of fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites. The key is the measurement of SCPE in the test. In Ref. 3, the chevron notch specimen is introduced to guarantee the process of stable growth in the tip of crack, which is suitable for brittle materials. When the crack propagates from the initial length a to $a+\Delta a$, SCPE is equal to the work of applied load subtracting the increment of elastic strain energy in specimens according to Griffith energy criterion that is:

$$\frac{d}{dA}(u-F+W)=0 \quad (1)$$

where A is surface of the crack; u is elastic strain energy; and W is fracture surface energy.

From eq.1 we can get SCPE:

$$G_i = (P^2/2b)dc/da \quad (2)$$

where c is the compliance of specimen, $c=y/P$, y is crack opening displacement, P is applied load; and b is the width of crack.

At the critical point, the SCPE is:

$$G_{ic} = (P_c^2/2b_c)(dc/da)_{a=a_c} \quad (3)$$

If $G_i \geq G_{ic}$, the crack propagates into the second stage.

3. EXPERIMENTS

The matrix is the glass-ceramic whose main components are SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and MgF_2 . The fiber used are T300 carbon fibers. The fabrication steps are: impregnate fibers with a slurry of finely divided glass-ceramic powder particles and binder; put the impregnated fibers to the model set, formed with 60-80 kg/cm; then heat to remove binder; sinter at about 1200 C in an inert atmosphere. After fabricated, the specimens are divided into two groups, one, cutting and finishing to 60x10x5 mm and notch with angle 60° in the middle, is for three-point bending test, another is with a chevron notch, notch width $S_1 \leq H/6$, $\theta=60^\circ$. Test is taken place in Shimadzu Universal Testing Machining AG2000A, the cross-head speed is 0.05 mm/min.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the test, we used a Data Microscope to monitor the tip of notch of specimen to distinguish the three fracture stages. At the beginning the deflection increases with the load, when the deflection is accumulated to a critical point, crack germinates, and propagates rapidly. This happens only in the second and third stage. Fig.4 shows the matrix crack when fibers remain intact. Results of test is in Table 1. In chevron

Fig.2 three-point bending specimen

Fig.3 specimen with chevron notch

notch specimen test, it is difficult to monitor the different stages with the Data Microscope. But further observations on fracture surface of broken specimen it would be found that in the nearby front surface of specimen, the surface is rough, the fibers pulled-out are longer (Fig.5), because the crack grows and stops in a stable

Table 1* Results of three-point bending test

No	a_0/W	a_0/H	a_0/b	P, N	y, mm
1	0.0364	0.1400	0.3730	150.8	0.2740
2	0.0360	0.1380	0.4285	169.3	0.3540
3	0.0276	0.1062	0.2584	202.3	0.2165
4	0.0220	0.0846	0.1571	181.2	0.1320
5	0.0276	0.1062	0.3399	143.0	0.1740
6	0.0200	0.0769	0.2370	188.0	0.0910
7	0.0396	0.1523	0.4876	115.5	0.1070
8	0.0192	0.0738	0.1959	218.8	0.1080

Table 2* Results of chevron notch specimen test

No	a_0/a_1	a_0/H	a_0/b	H/W	c, mm/KN	a-a ₀ , mm
1	0.2940	0.3125	0.0833	0.6153	5.529	0.2102
2	0.3000	0.4285	0.1000	0.5385	6.641	0.4913
3	0.3750	0.3529	0.1071	0.6538	9.245	1.021
4	0.2666	0.2857	0.0714	0.5385	20.307	1.467
5	0.3176	0.3375	0.090	0.6214	12.158	1.998
6	0.2900	0.3973	0.096	0.5615	11.045	2.423
7	0.3250	0.3250	0.0928	0.6231	16.643	2.731
8	0.2933	0.2821	0.0833	0.6005	19.826	3.341

* fiber-volume fraction is 10%

Fig.4 photo of crack in the matrix when fibers remain intact

Fig.5 photo of fracture surface

procedure; in the nearby the back surface, the surface is smooth, and fibers pulled-out are shorter, which shows the unstable propagation.

From eqs. (2)(3), the condition for crack propagation is:

$$(P^2/2)dc/da \geq G_{ic}b \quad (4)$$

For chevron notch specimen the width b is a variable, so we still have:

$$d/da((P^2/2)dc/da) \geq d/da(G_{ic}b) \quad (5)$$

Combining eqs. (4)(5):

$$(a_c - a_0)d^2c/da^2 - dc/da = 0 \quad (6)$$

Eq. (6) shows that the relation between the compliance and crack length is of an exponential function and express as:

$$c = A_0 e^{A_1(a_c - a_0)} \quad (7)$$

Where A_0 A_1 are constants, from Table 2 the value of A_0 A_1 can be determined and we can get:

$$a_c = 1/A_1 + a_0 \quad (8)$$

Substituting eq. (7) into eq.(2), the critical SCPE is derived:

$$G_{ic} = P_c^2 A_0 A_1 e / 2(a_c - a_0) \text{tg} \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (9)$$

From Fig.6 $A_0 = 7.935$ $A_1 = 0.2046$
and

$$G_{ic} = 4.4 \text{KJ/m}$$

For three-point bending test, if $G_{ip} = (F-u) = 1/2P^2c$, comparing G_{ic} and G_{ib} : we find G_{ic} is smaller than G_{ib} , in the experimental condition of this paper $G_{ic} = 0.89G_{ib}$, \bar{G}_{ib} is the average of G_{ib} .

5. CONCLUSIONS

According to hypothesis of three stages of crack propagation, the paper proposes the SCPE (eq.(9)) as the parameter for evaluating fracture toughness of composites, the effects of specimen sizes and other experimental condition have to be discussed further.

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Fig.6 relation between $\ln c$ and $(a - a_0)$